

GAYATRI BALASAMY V. ISG NOVASOFT TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED

AUTHOR'S NOTE:

This case brief has been prepared by **Rudraksh Vishwakarma** for academic purposes. It is an original work meant for legal study and educational reference only.

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CASE DETAILS

- 1. CITATION** - 2025 INSC 605
- 2. COURT** – SUPREME COURT
- 3. PARTY NAME** – Gayatri Balasamy v. ISG Novasoft Technologies Limited
- 4. CASE NUMBER** - SLP (C) Nos.15336-15337/2021; C.A. No.-006178-006179-2025
- 5. DIARY NUMBER** – 20788/2021

PARTIES INFORMATION

- 1. Applicant** - Gayatri Balasamy
- 2. Respondent** - ISG Novasoft Technologies Limited

ADVOCATES

- 1. For Applicant** - Senior Counsel Mr. Arvind Datar, Senior Counsel Mr. Darius Khambata, Senior Counsel Mr. Shekhar Naphade, Senior Counsel Mr. Ritin Rai, Senior Counsel Dr. Manish Singhvi, Counsel Mr. Abhishek Kumar Rao, Senior Counsel Counsel Mr. Pushkarma, Counsel M/s Ashwin Shanker, Counsel Vaibhav Dang, Counsel Mr. Amit George, Jinendra Jain, Counsel Mr. Pallav Mongolia.
- 2. For Respondent** – Solicitor General Tushar Mehta, Senior Counsel Saurabh Kripal, Senior Counsel Mr. Gourab Banerji, Senior Counsel Mr. Gaurav Pachnanda, Additional Solicitor General Ms. Archana Pathak Dave (ASG), Counsel Mr. Naresh Markanda, Counsel Mr. Surejendu Sankar Das, Counsel Mr. Saurav Agarwal, Counsel Mr. Saker Sikri, and Counsel Mr. Rahul G. Tanwani.

CORAM

1. SANJIV KHANNA, C.J.I.
2. B.R. GAVALI, J
3. P.V. SANJAY KUMAR, J
4. A.G. MASIH, J
5. K.V. VISHWANATHAN, J

Ratio – 4:1 (Constitutional Bench)

FACTS

The core issue arose from the referral order dated 20/02/2024 in the SLPs in *Gayatri Balasamy v. ISG Novasoft Technologies Limited*.¹ The Three-Judges bench directed the case to Five-Judges bench of the Supreme Court for an appropriate order as to the question arose regarding whether courts, under §§ 34 and 37 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996², possess the power to modify and arbitral award.

One line of decisions, notably *Project Director, NHAI vs. M. Hakeem and Anr.*³, held that courts do not have power to modify awards and can only set them aside on limited grounds. However, other benches of the Supreme Court (both Two-Judges and Three-Judges) (cases mentioned in Issue 5) had, in various cases, either modified arbitral award themselves or upheld High Court orders that had modified awards.

In this this case, the underlying facts of the *Gayatri Balasamy* case or other matters tagged are not of focus, rather, the main question of law is whether courts have power to modify awards.

ISSUES

1. Whether the powers of the Court under §§ 34 and 37 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 1996 will include the power to modify an arbitral award?
2. If the power to modify the award is available, whether such power can be exercised only where the award is severable, and a part thereof can be modified?

¹ 2024 SCC OnLine SC 1681.

² Hereinafter referred to as “1996 Act”.

³ (2021) 9 SCC 1.

3. Whether the power to set aside an award under § 34 of the Act, being a larger power, will include the power to modify an arbitral award and if so, to what extent?
4. Whether the power to modify an award can be read into the power to set aside an award under § 34 of the Act?
5. Whether the judgment of this Court in *Project Director NHAI vs. M. Hakeem*⁴, followed in *Larsen Air Conditioning and Refrigeration Company vs. Union of India*⁵, and *SV Samudram vs. State of Karnataka*⁶, lay down the correct law, as other benches of two Judges (in *Vedanta Limited vs. Shenzden Shandong Nuclear Power Construction Company Limited*⁷, *Oriental Structural Engineers Pvt. Ltd. vs. State of Kerala*⁸, and *M.P. Power Generation Co. Ltd. vs. Ansaldo Energia Spa*⁹) and three Judges (in *J.C. Budhraj vs. Chairman, Orissa Mining Corporation Ltd.*¹⁰, *Tata Hydroelectric Power Supply Co. Ltd. vs. Union of India*¹¹, and *Shakti Nath vs. Alpha Tiger Cyprus Investment No.3 Ltd.*¹²) of this Court have either modified or accepted modification of the arbitral awards under consideration?

OBSERVATIONS MADE BY THE COURT

A. Majority Opinion (CJI Sanjiv Khanna, BR Gavai J. Sanjay Kumar J, Augustine George Masih J)

1. The 1996 Act under § 5 intends minimal judicial intervention. § 34 limits recourse to courts primarily to an application for setting aside an award/
2. Proviso to § 34(2)(a)(iv) explicitly allows setting aside only a part of award if decisions on matters submitted to arbitration can be separated from those not submitted. The power to sever is inherent and elucidative. The *doctrine of omne majus continet in se minus*¹³ applied here. The power to set aside entire award includes the power to set aside a part if severable.

⁴ (2021) 9 SCC 1.

⁵ (2023) 15 SCC 472.

⁶ (2024) 3 SCC 623.

⁷ (2019) 11 SCC 465.

⁸ (2021) 6 SCC 150.

⁹ (2018) 16 SCC 661.

¹⁰ (2008) 2 SCC 444.

¹¹ (2003) 4 SCC 172.

¹² (2020) 11 SCC 685.

¹³ The greater includes the lesser.

Caveat: Partial setting aside is only possible if the “Valid” and “invalid” portions are legally and practically separable, not interdependent or inherently intertwined.

3. While distinct (modification alters, setting aside annuls), recognizing a limited modification power doesn’t inevitably lead to a merits review.
4. Limited power of Modification in § 34:
 - i. Denying courts any authority to modify, especially when it imposes hardships, increases costs, and causes delays, would defeat the *raison d’être*¹⁴ of arbitration. Forcing parties into a new arbitration for easily correctable issues is complicated.
 - ii. § 34 doesn’t restrict the range of reliefs a court can grant while remaining within statutory contours. Modification is more limited nuanced power than complete annulment. Silence in the Act isn’t a complete prohibition.
 - iii. The scope of it is that the courts can apply severability and modify a portion while retaining the rest, subjected to separability.
 - iv. Courts under § 34 possess inherent authority (similar to procedural review or § 152 CPC, 1908¹⁵ ¹⁶) to rectify clerical/computational/typographical error that don’t require a merits-based evaluation, even if § 33¹⁷ of the 1996 Act exists.
This is distinct from appellate review. If modification is debatable or error isn’t apparent, remand under § 34(4) or recourse to § 33 is appropriate.
5. Remand Power [§ 34(4)]:
 - i. This is a discretionary power to adjourn proceedings and give the arbitral tribunal an opportunity to resume proceedings or take corrective measure to eliminate grounds for setting aside.
 - ii. It is a curative mechanism, not for rewriting the award on merits.

¹⁴ It refers to the most important reason for someone of something’s existence. Basically, it means, “reason for being”, or “reason for existence”.

¹⁵ “**152. Amendment of judgments, decrees or orders.** — Clerical or arithmetical mistakes in judgments, decrees or orders or errors arising therein from any accidental slip or omission may at any time be corrected by the Court either of its own motion or on the application of any of the parties.”

¹⁶ Hereinafter referred to as “Code”.

¹⁷ “**Correction and interpretation of award; additional award.**” (refer 1996 Act).

- iii. The view in *Kinnari Mullick & Anr. vs. Ghanshyam Das Damani*,¹⁸ that a § 34(4) request must be in writing and before the § 34(1) application is decided was not fully accepted. An oral request is permissible. The § 37 appellate court also retains remand power under § 34(4).
 - iv. *I-Pay Clearing Services (P) Ltd. vs. ICICI Bank Ltd.*,¹⁹ was cited for the principle that § 34(4) is for clearing defects like lack of reasoning, not for review findings.
6. *Doctrine of Merger* and the New York Convention: The argument that court modification would make awards unenforceable under the New York Convention was rejected. § 48(1)(e) of the 1996 Act (and Article V of the New York Convention) recognizes that enforcement depends on the award becoming “binding” in terms of the law of the seat. If domestic law allows limited modification, it doesn’t inherently conflict.
 7. NHAIA Act – Expansive Modification of Arbitral Awards is Impermissible: The argument for expansive modification of powers in stator arbitrations (like under NHAIA Act) was rejected. § 34’s scope is uniform.
 8. Post-Award Interest [§31(7)]:
 - i. *Pendente lite*²⁰ Interest [§ 31(7)(a)]: If contrary to contract, the court can either set it aside or remand under § 34(4).
 - ii. Post-award interest [§ 31(7)(b)]: Courts retain the power to modify this. § 31(7)(b) provides a standard rate if the award is silent, i.e., the award itself does not specify the applicable post awards interest. Given that post-awards interest is future oriented and circumstances can change post-award, courts can intervene (increase or decrease) if facts justify, without acting in an appellate capacity. This is a unique Indian Legislative creation not found in UNCITRAL Model Law²¹.
 9. Post-Award Settlements: Parties can enter into settlements even after an award, governed by Order XXIII of the Code, provided its verifiable and lawful.

¹⁸ (2018) 11 SCC 328.

¹⁹ (2022) 3 SCC 121.

²⁰ “*Pendente lite*” means, “while the litigation is pending.”

²¹ Hereinafter referred to as “Model Law”.

10. Limitation Period [§ 43(4)]: If an award is set aside, the period between arbitration commencement and the court's setting-aside an order is excluded for limitation purpose for fresh proceedings.
11. Article²² 142²³ of the Constitution: The power is to be used with great care, in consonance with the 1996 Act's principles, not to rewrite awards on merits but to end protracted litigation and save costs/time.

B. Dissenting Opinion (Justice K.V. Vishwanathan)

Justice K.V. Vishwanathan largely dissented on the scope of modification, concurring on severability and correction of *actus curiae*²⁴ errors.

1. No power to "Modify" in § 34: Emphasized that "recourse" under § 34 is "only by an application for setting aside." The phrase "only if" limits grounds. Modification is qualitatively different from setting aside and it's a "lesser" power in this context.
2. Legitimate Intent & Model Law: The 1996 Act, based on the Model Law, deliberately omitted the power to modify, which existed in Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1940²⁵ (§ 15). If the Parliament intended to grant this power, it would've done it explicitly as other countries have. The Vishwanathan Committee recommended it, but the Parliament hasn't acted. Reading words into the statute is impermissible.
3. § 43(4) explicitly contemplates recommencement of arbitration after an award is set aside. Parties contractually oust court's jurisdiction, accepting the arbitral tribunal.
4. Appellate powers under Order XLI of the Code are vast (confirm, vary, reverse, remand, take evidence). § 34 powers are strictly circumscribed and not appellate.

²² Hereinafter referred to as "Art."

²³ "**142. Enforcement of decrees and orders of Supreme Court and orders as to discovery, etc.**— (1) The Supreme Court in the exercise of its jurisdiction may pass such decree or make such order as is necessary for doing complete justice in any cause or matter pending before it, and any decree so passed or order so made shall be enforceable throughout the territory of India in such manner as may be prescribed by or under any law made by Parliament and, until provision in that behalf is so made, in such manner as the President may by order prescribe.

(2) Subject to the provisions of any law made in this behalf by Parliament, the Supreme Court shall, as respects the whole of the territory of India, have all and every power to make any order for the purpose of securing the attendance of any person, the discovery or production of any documents, or the investigation or punishment of any contempt of itself."

²⁴ "*Actus Curiae*" means, an act of the court shall prejudice no one."

²⁵ Hereinafter referred to as "1940 Act".

5. Inherent Powers (§ 151 of the Code) and Implied Powers: These cannot be used to conflict with express statutory provisions or legitimate intent. The *doctrine of implied powers* is for effectuating a granted power where impossible otherwise, not applicable here as setting aside is fully effectuated by annulment.
6. Party Autonomy: A core principle. Parties choose arbitrators with its defined, limited judicial review. Granting modification power undermines this.
7. Art. 142: Cannot be used to “supplant” substantive law or achieve indirectly what cannot be done directly. Modifying an award under Art. 142 would conflict with statutory scheme of the 1996 Act.
8. New York Convention Complications: If Indian courts modify awards, enforcement abroad becomes problematic as it’s no longer purely the “arbitral award” but a court-altered decision, potentially breaching the convention unless specific domestic litigation (like UK English Arbitration Act’s § 71) clarifies the status of the modified law.
9. § 33 and § 34(4) as “Safety Valves”:
 - i. § 33: Arbitrator’s power to correct computational, clerical, typographical errors, or give interpretations/additional awards.
 - ii. § 34(4) (Remand): A crucial tool. If grounds for setting aside exists, the court (even *suo motu*, and an oral request is sufficient, disagreeing with ***Kinnari Mullick***²⁶ on written request) can adjourn and remit to the tribunal to eliminate those grounds (e.g., provide reasons, cure procedural defects). This does not mean that the court dictates changes on merits.
10. Correcting of computational/clerical/typographical errors by court: A very limited exception. Based on the maxim *actus curiae neminem gravabit*, if the arbitrator fails to correct such patent errors (under § 33) or rejects a request mechanically, the § 34 court can correct them without altering the award’s substance. This is not “modification” in the broader sense.
11. Interest cannot be modified under § 34 by the court. If interest is problematic, the award can be set aside, or the matter remitted under § 34(4) for the arbitrator to reconsider.

²⁶ (*Supra*).

12. Proviso to § 34(2)(a)(iv) and General Principle is fully endorsed, if an award deals with multiple claims, and some are bad, and some are bad, the court can sever and set aside only the bad parts, provided they are not inseparable intertwined with the good parts. This is consistent with precedent like *J.G. Engineers (P) Ltd. vs. Union of India & Anr.*²⁷
13. *M Hakeem* not *Per Incuriam*: M Hakeem correctly held no power to modify. Cases cited for modification were distinguishable (e.g., *Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Limited vs. Western GECO International Limited*²⁸ involved severability, *Shakti Nath vs. Alpha Tiger Cyprus Investment No. 3 Ltd.* was by consent.

CONTENTIONS OF BOTH THE PARTIES

In Favor of Modification

1. Mr. Arvind Datar (Sr. Counsel):

- i. Argued for reading words (“and, to the extent,” “or modified”) into § 34 to avoid absurdity and injustice, citing instances where courts added words.
- ii. Contended *M. Hakeem* was *per incuriam* as it conflicted with prior larger/co-ordinate bench decisions that had modified awards.
- iii. Stated that only setting aside causes hardship (re-arbitration).
- iv. Argued power to “set-aside” includes the lesser power to “modify” (*omne majus continet in se minus*)

2. Mr. Darius Khambata (Sr. Counsel):

- i. Contended that foreign jurisdictions statutorily allowing modifications.
- ii. Citing, “Mustill & Boyd” on Commercial Arbitration, argued an obviously wrong decision should be correctable by the court, and any consequential variation is justified.
- iii. Modification ensure speedy, effective, inexpensive, and expeditious dispute resolution.
- iv. Referred to the Dr. T.K. Vishwanathan Committee Report recommending legislative change for modification.

²⁷ (2011) 5 SCC 785.

²⁸ (2014) 9 SCC 263.

- v. Argued that silence in the Act isn't a prohibition. Courts should "iron out the creases."

3. Mr. Shekhar Naphade (Sr. Counsel):

- i. Distinguished grounds: If an award grants relief based on § 34(2)(i), (ii), (iv), (v) or § 34(2)(b)(i) defects, no modification is possible, only setting aside.
- ii. However, for issues like violation of natural justice or corruption, mere setting aside doesn't end the *lis* and defeats the purpose of resolving disputes expeditiously. The court should modify/substitute to do what the tribunal ought to have done.
- iii. § 34 application is heard by a "Court" [§ 2(1)(e)], so general inherent powers (§ 151 of the Code) apply.

4. Mr. Ritin Rai (Sr. Counsel):

- i. "Recourse" is a wider term. No prohibition to modify in the Act.
- ii. If modification axiomatically follows a finding, it should be allowed.

5. Dr. Manish Singhvi (Sr. Counsel) & Mr. Abhishek Kumar Rao: Reiterated others, Dr. Singhvi specifically argued that NHAH competent authorities aren't legally trained, so their award shouldn't be final, and § 34 courts should have power to enhance.

6. Mr. Pushkarma (Sr. Counsel) m/s Ashwin Shanker, Vaibhav Dang, Amit George, Jinendra Jain:

- i. Reiterated Datar and Khamabata.
- ii. **Vaibhav Dang & Jinendra Jain:** Added that re-arbitration is costly. Hakeem didn't consider modification by mutual consent or correction of critical errors by § 34 court.
- iii. **Amit George:** Power to grant/reduce/increase interest should be read into § 34 without fresh arbitration, especially if contrary to contract.

7. Mr. Pallav Mongolia: Any modification should be via § 34(4) mechanism. Procedural pre-conditions in § 34(4) should be read as discretionary.

Against Modification

1. Mr. Tushar Mehta (Solicitor General):

- i. Power to modify must be statutorily conferred.

- ii. Cited foreign statutes with express modification powers (UK, USA, Singapore, Canada), contrasting with Indian Act's silence.
- iii. § 34 (like Model Law) has limited grounds for setting-aside. Model Law debates show that setting-aside was the only recourse.
- iv. § 34(4) (remit) is intended to prevent annulment on specific grounds.
- v. 76th Law Commission report didn't recommend modification power to 1996 Act, despite its existing in 1940 Act.
- vi. Setting-aside is not akin to appeal; modification is not subsumed in "set-aside", they are different judicial planes.
- vii. § 5 of the 1996 Act mandates limited intervention. Art. 142 cannot contravene statute.

2. Mr. Saurabh Kripal (Sr. Counsel):

- i. Courts cannot modify clear statutory words. The 1996 Act has worked well.
- ii. "Setting-aside" means quashing. Permitting modification delays proceedings and creates uncertainty, which is anathema to commerce. Speedy justice is for Parliament to address.
- iii. Party autonomy and non-interference are key. Modification drags courts into merits review.
- iv. *Omne Majus* principle inapplicable as powers are not of the same genus.

3. Gourab Banerji (Sr. Counsel):

- i. Model Law and 1996 Act permits only "setting-aside." Countries derogating have specific empowering provisions.
- ii. Power to annul is inconsistent with power to appeal. No judicially manageable standards for modification contours; legislation is the only way.
- iii. § 34(4) for curing defects (no reasoning, gaps in reasoning), not reconsideration on merits.
- iv. Severability is possible for distinct claims.
- v. Enforcement issues (New York Convention): Modification by court leads to enforcement problems abroad, as the enforcement issue is no longer purely the "arbitral awards". Other jurisdictions have specified laws (e.g. § 71 of the English Arbitration Act, § 5(7) of Schedule 2 of the New Zealand Arbitration Act, 1996, and § 39(5) of the Kenyan Arbitration Act, 1995) to deal with this.

4. Mr. Gaurav Pachnanda (Sr. Counsel):

- i. Severability is possible only if portions are identifiable and not intermingled (e.g., netted claims in a composite award are hard to sever).
 - ii. *Doctrine of merger* doesn't apply to § 34 orders, as the court's power isn't identical to the tribunal. Modification/variation is not envisaged § 151 of the Code cannot be used if § 34 is clear.
5. **Ms. Archana Pathak Dave (ASG), Mr. Naresh Markanda, Mr. Surejendu Sankar Das, Mr. Saurav Agarwal, Mr. Saker Sikri, and Mr. Rahul G. Tanwani:** Reiterated the above submissions against modifications.

JUDGEMENT

A. Majority Opinion (CJI Sanjiv Khanna, BR Gavai J. Sanjay Kumar J, Augustine George Masih J)

The court has a limited power under §§ 34 and 37 of the 1996 Act to modify the arbitral awards under these circumstances:

1. **Severability:** When the awards is severable, by the severing the “invalid” portion from the “valid” portion (as per Part II of their Analysis²⁹). This effectively modifies the award by upholding only part of it.
2. **Clerical/Computational/Typographical Errors:** By correcting any such errors that appears erroneous on the face of the record (as per Part IV and V of their Analysis).
3. **Post-Award Interest:** May be modified in some circumstances (as per Part IX on their Analysis).
4. **Art. 142 of the Constitution:** Applies, *albeit*, the power must be exercised with great care and caution and within constitutional limits (as per Part XII of their Analysis).

B. Dissenting Opinion (K.V. Vishwanathan J)

Justice Vishwanathan delivered the referred questions as follows:

1. **Question 1 (Power to Modify):** Courts under § 34 and in appeal do not have the power to modify the arbitral award.

²⁹ In the judgement Analysis is starting from page 15 (of 61) and end to page 36 (of 61).

2. **Question 2 (Modification and Severance):** Modification and severance are different. Modification is not permitted. Severance of an award falling foul of § 34 is permissible if parts are severable.
3. **Questions 3 & 4 (Modify as lesser power):** Power to set-aside does not include power to modify. They are qualitatively different powers.
4. **Question 5 (Correctness of *M Hakeem*):** M Hakeem, in holding no power to modify, lays down the correct law.

The only exception for the § 34 court is to carry out corrections in computational, clerical, or typographical errors or other similar errors, based on the principle of *actus curiae neminem gravabit*.

He also held:

1. *Kinnari Mullick*³⁰ incorrect in holding a § 34(4) request must be written; an oral request suffices.
2. § 34(4) can be exercised *suo motu* by the court.

REASONING FOR THE JUDGEMENT

A. Reasoning for the Majority Opinion: The judges adopted a balanced approach, recognizing the legislative purpose of minimal intervention while acknowledging court's inherent, though restricted, authority to ensure justice, without re-examining the merits of the case. They found scope for modification in the four points of their judgement mentioned before.

B. Reasoning for the Dissenting Opinion:

Following is the reasoning for the dissenting opinion of Justice K.V. Vishwanathan:

1. He emphasized a textual and purposive interpretation of the 1996 Act. He stressed that unlike the 1940 Act, the 1996 Act based on the Model Law intentionally omits any provision for modifying arbitral awards, and courts cannot read such power into the statute.
2. Any judicial power must be expressly conferred or be necessary incident to an express power; modification is not. "Setting-aside" means annulment, not alteration.

³⁰ (*Supra*).

3. The “hardship” of re-arbitration is contemplated by the § 43(4) of the 1996 Act itself.
4. Party autonomy means parties accept the limited judicial review framework.
5. Reading in power to modify would be judicial litigation.
6. Art. 142 should not be used to supplant statutory provisions.
7. The only “correction” a § 34 court can do is for patent computational/clerical/typographical errors under the *actus curia* principle, which is not substantive legislation.
8. He agreed with the majority of the principle of severability and the interpretation of § 34(4) regarding the nature of the request.
9. His primary divergence was on the power to modify interest and the broader application of Art. 142 for modification by the Supreme Court in § 34 matters.

CONCLUSION

The Supreme Court clarified how much power judges have over decisions made by the arbitrators. The main rule is that the judges can’t just rewrite the arbitrator’s award if they dissent from the outcome. Their main role is to check for serious errors in how arbitration was done or if the awards was against the public policy, and if so, they can cancel the award.

The court also said judges can make some limited changes like, they can remove bad parts of an award if the good parts can still stand on their own, fix clerical mistakes, typographical, or calculation errors, and in some cases, adjust the interest to be paid after the award. The Supreme Court also has special power for unique cases. So, while major changes are off-limits, minor, specific changes are for to avoid multiple-rounds of arbitration.

MY UNDERSTANDING

The Supreme Court endorsed that the courts generally can’t change an arbitrator’s core decision (merits) under § 34. Their main role is to cancel awards for serious flaws, not to acts as a higher appellate court.

Though, limited modifications are now clarified, that is, courts can sever and uphold valid parts of an award if the bad parts are separable, and correct obvious clerical or calculation errors. The majority also allowed courts to adjust post-award interest in specific cases and for the

Supreme Court to use Art. 142 for complete justice. This aims to avoid re-arbitration for minor, fixable issues while respecting arbitration's finality.